

COMPARATIVE MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE WORKING SURFACE OF ENDODONTIC ROTARY NICKEL TITANIUM INSTRUMENTS AFTER MAXIMUM CYCLIC LOADING.

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Relevance

The use of rotating nickel-titanium endodontic instruments: protapers (PTu, Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland), Ultrataper (Ultrataper Eurofle, Shenzhen, China) and Super Files (Superfle, Eurofle, Shenzhen, China) is widespread practice of clinical activity of a dentist [1-3, 5]. The results of studies of cyclic fatigue of a rotating nickel-titanium endodontic instrument allows a dentist to make a choice of tools when solving various clinical problems [4-7]. According to literary sources, the study of the surfaces of endodontic instruments of rotating nickel-titanium instruments, in particular protapers, occupies a leading place in modern endodontic practice [5, 6]. Thus, understanding the influence of mechanical loads on the working surfaces of nickel-titanium rotating tools can provide useful practical information in terms of the formation of surface defects and clinical safety [2, 3].

Researches

Morphometric analysis of the working surfaces of various types of protapers after they receive maximum cyclic loads.

Materials and methods

The chemical composition and physical properties of three types of machine tools are analyzed F2 of various types: protapers Universal (PTu, Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland), Ultrataper (Ultrataper, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) and superfile (Superfile, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China). The new tool was removed from the blister pack and was not autoclaved. According to the standard method of working with nickel-titanium rotary instruments (PTu), 75 endo-Training-Blocks were processed using the VDW Silver endomotor until the tool was broken off by one operator within 10 days. The blocks were divided into three comparison groups: 25 endoblocks processed by Universal protapers (PTu, Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland), 25 endoblocks – ultrapers (Ultrataper, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) and 25 blocks – superfiles (Superfile, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China). An apical stop was formed for each endodontic block using manual k-files with diameters of 6, 8, 10 and 15. Machine files were used

sequentially SX, S1, S2, F1, F2, F3. 3-5 passive pecking movements in the apical direction were performed by a rotary nickel-titanium instrument inserted into the channel, when the working length is reached, the rotating file is immediately removed from the endblock channel. After each file, the irrigation of the endoblock was carried out with a 3.25% solution of sodium hypochlorite, 17% EDTA gel was used as an endolubricant. The criteria for the quality of treatment of the walls of the endoblock were the shape of the channel in the form of a truncated cone, the smoothness of the walls, the irrigation solution did not go beyond the apical opening due to the formed stop [1].

Results

The maximum plastic deformation and destruction of the superfile (Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) occurred on the 20th endoblock, the ultrataper (Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) – on the 10th endoblock, the Universal proteiper (PTu, Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) – on the 5th endoblock. Thus, the percentage of F2 instrument breakdowns of Universal protapers was 20%, ultrapers – 12%, superfiles – 4% of the total number of broken endodontic files, which coincides with the data of literary sources [5]. The value of the Pearson coefficient for nickel – 0.126 and titanium - 0.054 in the area of the working face of the endodontic instrument F2 indicates a linear dependence on the increased concentration of these metals on an increase in the probability of breaking off the tip of the proteiper ($p < 0,05$). The diagram shows the correlation of the chemical composition of the rotating nickel-titanium tool F2 from the resistance to the maximum cyclic load. Superfile (Superfile, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China).

Conclusions

1. The morphometric analysis revealed a difference in the structure of the metal alloy of the protapers F2 with a comparable nickel content (46-52%) and titanium (38-41%).
2. The content of pure nickel-titanium alloy along the periphery of the endodontic instrument in Universal protapers (PTu, Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) provide high cutting capacity of the faces. More uniform structure of ultrataper (Ultrataper Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) and Superfile, (Superfile, Eurofile, Shenzhen, China) may give greater resistance to cyclical loads.
3. The data obtained on the different resistance to cyclic loads of F2 protapers should be taken into account in the endodontic treatment of multi-root teeth.
4. The analysis of the structure of the nickel-titanium alloy indicates the predetermination of the development of the fracture of the tool with prolonged use and the need to take into account the cycles of the endodontic rotary tool.

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